

Codebook Survey: Information Technology Governance in Colombian Enterprises

ID_Register	Description	Options
1_Timestap	Date survey was conducted	Metadata
2_Position_Nearby	Position is closest to your level of work	Analyst Professional Supervisor Manager Director Vice President President/CEO External Consultant Academic Intern
2_2_Professional Title	Education (undergrade degree)	Open Answer
2_1_Position_Specific	Specific position in the organization	Open Answer
3_Number_of_Employees_Org	Number of people employed in the company, including all branches, divisions and subsidiaries.	0-10 10-50 50-250 Over 250
4_Coverage_Org	Territorial scope where the company is present	International Local/Regional National
5_City_Org	Location where the person completing the survey works.	Open Answer
6_Country_Org	Country where the person completing the survey works.	Open Answer
7_Type_Org	Origin of the capital of the organization or company where the person completing the survey works.	Private Public. Mixed
8_Sector_Org	Economic sector of the organization or company where the person completing the survey works.	Industrial / Commercial Technology Services Government Education Goods and Services Health
9_IT_Officce	Existence of an IT department or management in the organization.	Yes No
10_Importance_IT	Importance of information and technology for the strategy and vision of your company for the executive team.	Very Important Not Very Important. Don't Know
11_IT_involvement_level	Level of involvement of the company's management in IT governance.	High Low Moderate Uncertain

12_IT_investment _plan_Current	IT-related investment plan for the next 12 months.	<p>Selective growth based on potential/expected contribution to business value Uncertain Generalized increase Reduce across the board Freeze at current level Reduce selectively based on potential/expected contribution to business value. Don't know.</p>
13_Current use_IT	Current use of emerging and new technology to support processes.	<p>Data Mining. Business Intelligence. Big Data. Artificial Intelligence. Virtual Reality / Augmented Reality. Social Networking. Robotics/Process Automation. Others None</p>
14_Future use_IT	Technologies that the organization where the respondent works plans to implement in the short or medium term.	<p>Data Mining. Business Intelligence. Big Data. Artificial Intelligence. Virtual Reality / Augmented Reality. Social Networking. Robotics/Process Automation. Others None</p>
15_Problems_IT	Aspects that the company has experienced in the last 12 months as a result of an IT-related problem/incident.	<p>Incurring unexpected expenses. Reputation was damaged. Customer satisfaction was reduced. Cost reduction opportunities were delayed or lost. A competitor beat my company to market. None. Other.</p>
16_Use_marco/est andar_TI ?	Does your company use a framework/standard for governance and management/governance/ EA or IT services?	<p>Yes No I do not know</p>
17_TOGAF	If yes, which framework/standard is used? TOGAF	<p>Yes = 1 No= 0</p>
17_ITIL	Does your organization use a framework/standard for governance and management/governance/ EA or IT services? ITIL	<p>Yes = 1 No= 0</p>

17_ZACHMAN	If yes, which framework/standard is used? ZACHMAN	Yes = 1 No= 0
17_COBIT	Does your company use a framework/standard for governance and management/governance/ EA or IT services? COBIT	Yes = 1 No= 0
17_ISO	If yes, which framework/standard is used? ISO	Yes = 1 No= 0
17_CMMI	Does your company use a framework/standard for governance and management/governance/ EA or IT services? CMMI	Yes = 1 No= 0
17_OTHERS	If yes, which framework/standard is used? OTHERS	Yes = 1 No= 0
18_Problems_IT_Last6Month	IT-related problems experienced by the company in the last 12 months.	High IT cost with low or unknown return on investment. Project cost overruns. Security breaches. Inadequate IT staffing. Inadequate disaster recovery or business continuity measures. Lack of innovation. Serious IT operation incidents. Outsourcing issue. None. Other. Don't know
19_Cancelado_proyecto_TI	Termination or cancellation of an IT-related project before it is fully implemented	Yes No Don't know
20_If CP_select the reason	If yes to the above answer, please select the reason	Changes in business needs. Failed to deliver what was promised. Exceeded budget. Did not support business strategy. No other reason for cancellation. Other Reasons for cancellation
20-benefits	Perceived benefits of IT adoption or implementation	Improved customer service. New or improved products and services. Cost reduction. Improved business intelligence. Improved information security. All of the above. Not applicable.